

Bridging borders through study abroad: Introducing the Corpus of Written Spanish- L2 and Heritage- Study Abroad (COWS-L2H-SA)

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Few learner corpora have captured language learning longitudinally during study abroad (SA), with the notable exception of the LANGSNAP corpus (Mitchell et al., 2017). SA has been found to provide opportunities for enhanced language learning, although the affordances of SA may vary based on program features and students' individual differences (Pérez-Vidal & Sanz, 2023). Given the heterogeneity of learning outcomes between different programs and students, it is imperative that SA-focused learner corpora capture a greater variety of program types and student profiles.

To fill this gap, this poster will present the Corpus of Written Spanish- L2 and Heritage- Study Abroad (COWS-L2H-SA), an addition to COWS-L2H (Yamada et al, 2020) that includes students from the same U.S. university who study abroad for 2.5 months. The students participate in one of two Spanish language-focused programs in Argentina or Spain. The participant sample includes both L2 and heritage language learners and participants from beginner, intermediate, and advanced proficiency levels. The corpus showcases writing that students complete at the beginning, middle, end, and two months after their SA program. In the task, students make requests via emails written to interlocutors differing in social distance— a professor and a student.

In the poster, I will present preliminary findings about students' longitudinal writing development during and after SA in terms of (1) global communicative effectiveness (based on expert ratings) and (2) lexical complexity, which encompasses lexical diversity (mean textual lexical diversity; MTLD), lexical density (ratio of content to total words), and lexical sophistication (mean frequency of content words in the EsPal reference corpus; Duchon et al., 2013). By contextualizing students' writing development through information about their learner profiles and engagement with features of their SA program, this study increases understanding of the diverse manners in which language learning can occur (un)successfully during SA.

References

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